

"INFLUENCE OF IRON-DEFICIENCY ANEMIA ON THE COURSE OF PREGNANCY COMPLICATED BY EMBRYOTROPHOBLASTIC INSUFFICIENCY

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Iron-deficiency anemia ranks among the leading extragenital conditions in pregnant women due to the significantly increased iron requirements during pregnancy, primarily driven by the high demands of the placenta and the developing fetus. Modern data indicate that iron deficiency develops in all pregnant women by the end of the pregnancy period. Iron requirements steadily increase during pregnancy, with an increase of 1 mg/day in the first trimester, 2 mg/day in the second trimester, and 3-5 mg/day in the third trimester. The greatest iron loss occurs between the 16th and 20th weeks of pregnancy, coinciding with the onset of fetal hematopoiesis and the increase in maternal blood volume. However, considering the fact that only 2.5 mg of iron is absorbed from food daily, while from medicinal preparations, it is 15-20 times higher, iron supplements are the preferred means of correcting iron deficiency.

It is recommended to prescribe preparations containing Fe²⁺, FeSO₄, because of their better absorption. The daily dose for the prevention of anemia and the treatment of a mild form of the disease is 50-60 mg of Fe²⁺, and for the treatment of severe anemia, it is 100-120 mg of Fe²⁺. Iron sulfate 320 mg (equivalent to 100 mg of Fe²⁺) is taken orally 2 times a day, strictly 1 hour before or 2 hours after meals, as other food ingredients can affect absorption.

Taking iron supplements orally is the most preferable method, rather than injections, as the latter can often lead to various side effects: constipation, bloating, diarrhea, heartburn, stomach pain, nausea, and dark stools.

Research Objective: To study the influence of varying degrees of iron-deficiency anemia on the course and outcome of the first-trimester pregnancy complicated by a threat of miscarriage.

Materials and methods: To achieve the set goal, a clinical and laboratory examination was conducted on 30 pregnant women in the first trimester of gestation (6-12 weeks) with iron-deficiency anemia in combination with embryotrophoblastic insufficiency.

Results and Discussion: The analysis revealed several characteristic features in the studied patients, including a high frequency of infectious diseases, coexisting conditions outside the reproductive system, especially in the digestive system,

chronic infectious foci, menstrual and reproductive function disorders, as well as complications in previous pregnancies. Iron-deficiency anemia was identified in 12 (40%) women in their previous pregnancies. Among the studied pregnant women, 6 (20%) were prim parous, and 9 (30%) were multiparous. Of the 28 (94%) women expecting a subsequent birth, only 11 (38%) had previously given birth naturally. Four (16%) patients had a history of spontaneous miscarriages, and three women (10%) experienced missed pregnancies. All patients complained of general weakness, fatigue, sleep disturbances, and unpleasant lower abdominal pain. To confirm the diagnosis of iron-deficiency anemia, we analyzed peripheral blood parameters, including hemoglobin (Hb) levels, the number of erythrocytes, and the color index (CI). Serum iron (Fe) and ferritin (SF) levels were also used to assess iron stores. The severity of iron-deficiency anemia was determined based on hemoglobin levels. Twenty pregnant women had mild anemia (hemoglobin reduction from 90 to 110 g/L), and ten had moderate anemia (hemoglobin reduction from 70 to 89 g/L).

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Conclusion: Thus, studying the parameters of complete blood count, particularly hemoglobin, erythrocyte count, and the color index in peripheral blood, and timely correction of these deviations contribute to the preservation of pregnancy and are one of the factors in preventing embryotrophoblastic insufficiency.

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